

Craftdash:

Building trustworthy
cultural AI at startup scale

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Topic overview

This case study explores how **Craftdash Limited** is developing Culture Illustro, an AI-powered platform designed to generate culturally accurate, high-trust visual content for use in education, storytelling and design. Built within the constraints of a small UK-based startup, the project focuses on embedding governance, provenance and cultural integrity directly into the data and development lifecycle.

Participation in Bridge AI – The Turing Way Practitioners Hub has supported this work by strengthening Craftdash’s use of systems thinking, stakeholder mapping, data readiness frameworks and lightweight governance-by-design. Together, these approaches enable the team to build responsible AI systems without the heavy operational burden typically associated with enterprise-scale governance.

Why non-Western cultural AI needs a different approach

Generative AI is rapidly transforming how content is created across the creative economy. Yet many models struggle to represent non-Western and underrepresented cultures accurately. Outputs may appear plausible but contain subtle errors such as misrepresenting practices, mixing symbols, or simplifying cultural meaning into generic visual templates. These risks were noted by a **UNESCO Independent Expert Group in a recent report on AI and culture.**

For Craftdash, this presents both a risk and an opportunity. Founder Olugbenga Latinwo explains that the problem is not simply technical: it is rooted in how cultural data is sourced, structured and interpreted.

Culture Illustro was created to address this gap. The platform aims to support creators, educators and cultural organisations in generating illustrations that are not only visually compelling, but also culturally grounded and trustworthy.

This is particularly important in domains such as education and public storytelling, where inaccurate outputs can spread quickly and become accepted as ‘common knowledge’. Craftdash therefore adopts a governance-first approach: cultural integrity is treated as a design requirement from the outset, rather than something to be corrected after deployment.

Culture Illustro and culturally grounded AI

Culture Illustro is designed to generate culturally accurate vector illustrations for a range of use cases, including:

- educational materials and lesson content
- cultural storytelling and media production
- design and branding projects
- exhibitions and digital heritage outputs.

Instead of relying on large, unstructured datasets, the system is built on small, curated ‘concept packs’: collections of culturally specific visual assets such as attire, artefacts, environments and ceremonial scenes.

Each asset is accompanied by structured metadata capturing:

- cultural context (location, time period, meaning)
- provenance (creator, permissions, attribution rules)
- cultural safety considerations (what should not be depicted or remixed).

This approach allows the system to learn cultural meaning, not just visual style.

Olugbenga says: “Rather than prompting a model to invent a generic ‘African royal scene’ – which can blur or mix cultural signals – we start with a clearly defined cultural concept and context. This could be, for example, a specific ceremonial setting from the Yoruba culture of West Africa, with the correct regalia, environment and gestures. The goal is that the system learns cultural meaning, not just visual style, so it doesn’t default to generic or mixed representations that feel plausible but are actually wrong.”

Data foundations, governance and systems thinking

Structured cultural data and provenance

Craftdash's approach begins with carefully curated datasets built through collaboration with verified cultural contributors. Each dataset follows a repeatable pipeline:

- a defined cultural brief specifying scope, boundaries and meaning
- contributor onboarding and alignment on cultural safety rules
- asset creation guided by the brief
- structured metadata capture
- cultural peer review
- governance checks (permissions, attribution, restrictions)
- versioned dataset release with traceable documentation.

By enforcing minimum metadata requirements – such as locality, time period and meaning notes – the team reduces the likelihood that the model will 'guess' missing context.

Versioning is also central. Each dataset release is tracked, with clear records of what changed and why. This enables traceability if outputs are challenged or require correction.

Yoruba_Illustration_Training_Data_Yoruba_Kings_Greeting_Each_Other.png
Courtesy: Craftdash Sample Illustration Dataset, shared under CC-BY with permission

Governance-by-design

Craftdash embeds governance into the system from the start, rather than being retrofitted at the end of the process. Key elements include:

- dataset documentation describing scope, limitations and restrictions
- model documentation outlining intended use and known limitations
- cultural risk logs tracking potential harms and mitigations
- provenance and consent records for all assets
- version control and audit trails.

These artefacts provide a lightweight but defensible governance structure. They allow the team to explain how outputs were generated and to respond quickly when issues arise.

Importantly, governance is designed to remain manageable within SME constraints, prioritising clarity and repeatability over complex compliance frameworks.

Systems thinking across the AI lifecycle

Craftdash applies systems thinking to map the entire lifecycle of Culture Illustro – from data creation through to user interaction. This approach has revealed several critical insights:

- Cultural errors often originate upstream, in poorly defined briefs or incomplete metadata.
- Communities represented in outputs are stakeholders, even if they are not direct users.
- Trade-offs exist between speed, variety and cultural accuracy.
- Human workflow pressures can influence model outputs, even without malicious intent.

In response, the team introduced targeted safeguards at key points in the lifecycle, including:

- mandatory context requirements before training
- cultural review checkpoints
- risk-tiered generation for sensitive content
- feedback mechanisms for correcting outputs

This approach ensures that governance is embedded where it has the greatest impact, rather than applied uniformly across all stages.

“Culture Illustro Lifecycle Pipeline (Connected Stages)”

Image: Craftdash's Culture Illustro Lifecycle Pipeline, source: CraftDash

Challenges: Building responsibly under constraints

Limited in-house expertise and resources

As a small startup, Craftdash faces challenges in accessing both AI engineering expertise and culturally informed governance capabilities. Rather than relying on large in-house teams, the company uses structured templates, micro-reviews and external contributors to maintain quality.

Cost and compute constraints

Generative AI development can be resource-intensive. Craftdash adopts a compute-efficient approach, training models only when datasets are sufficiently mature and using small-scale experiments to validate improvements before scaling.

Evolving governance expectations

Regulatory expectations around AI transparency, accountability and data rights are rapidly evolving. Craftdash addresses this by building modular governance artefacts that can adapt over time.

Cultural misrepresentation risks

One of the most significant challenges is avoiding 'plausible but wrong' outputs. Without sufficient context, models can default to generic or dominant cultural templates. Craftdash mitigates this by prioritising data quality, cultural review and restricted depiction rules.

Fragmented cultural data ecosystems

Many cultural domains lack structured, high-quality datasets. Craftdash addresses this through collaborative sourcing and small-batch dataset development, prioritising depth over scale.

Next steps: Scaling through collaboration and partnership

The next phase of Culture Illustro focuses on scaling responsibly and at an appropriate speed. Craftdash is prioritising partnerships that support:

- co-creation of culturally grounded datasets
- expansion of contributor and reviewer networks
- strengthening of governance and validation processes
- broader participation from cultural institutions and educators.

Alongside pilot collaborations, the team is building a network of long-term partners across four areas:

- governance and assurance
- technical development
- cultural and heritage organisations
- education and public engagement.

The goal is to move from a governance-led prototype to a stable, usable system while maintaining cultural integrity and trust.

To support this transition, Craftdash is also seeking non-dilutive funding to expand dataset coverage, improve evaluation processes and strengthen user-facing features.

Key takeaways

- Non-Western and underrepresented cultures are particularly at risk of inaccurate representation through generative AI models.
- Cultural integrity must be built into AI systems at the data and workflow level, not added later.
- High-quality, context-rich datasets are essential for reducing misrepresentation.
- Governance-by-design can be implemented at startup scale through lightweight, repeatable processes.
- Systems thinking helps identify where risks originate and where safeguards are most effective.
- Small teams can build responsible AI by prioritising key control points.
- Collaboration with cultural contributors and stakeholders is critical to maintaining trust and accuracy.

Reflections on *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub

“Building Culture Illustro made one thing clear to us: cultural integrity can’t be ‘checked in’ at the end of AI development – it has to be built into the data, the workflow and the release process from day one. The biggest risks don’t start at deployment; they start earlier, when briefs are vague, context is missing, or ‘thin data’ forces the model to guess. Those guesses can look convincing, spread quickly, and become accepted as common knowledge even when they’re wrong. The Practitioners Hub came at exactly the right time. It took us back to fundamentals – cultural meaning, provenance and trust – and gave us practical tools we could apply immediately. Through systems thinking, stakeholder mapping and data readiness frameworks, we mapped our lifecycle end-to-end, identified hidden stakeholders, and turned abstract governance principles into concrete controls we could actually run. The result has been speed with discipline: clearer decisions, safeguards placed where risks enter, and evidence structured in a way partners and users can trust.”

Olugbenga Latinwo,
Founder, Craftdash

Contributors and acknowledgements

This case study is published under *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub* 2025–26 Cohort – case study series. The Practitioners Hub is *The Turing Way* project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2025, The Turing Way team welcomed **Olugbenga Latinwo** and **Priscilla Latinwo**, founders of Craftdash, as Experts-in-Residence to discuss and share their implementation approaches to data science and AI, as well as build additional skills around best practices in responsible, ethical, and collaborative working. We thank them for leading the development of this case study.

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub's 2025–26 Cohort was co-delivered by **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher – Open Source Practices and Dr Ann Borda, Senior Research Community Manager. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager and **Arielle Bennett**, the Case Study Liaison for this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Malvika Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: theturingway@gmail.com

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Artificial Intelligence and Culture – Report from the Independent Expert Group – 2025

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